

Archaeology in Development Management

Its Contribution in
England, Scotland
& Wales

This report was commissioned by The Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers (ALG AO:UK), which provides a forum for archaeologists working for local authorities and national parks throughout the UK. Members include metropolitan authorities, shire counties, unitary authorities, London boroughs, national parks and historic cities, towns and boroughs across England, Wales and Scotland as well as representatives from Northern Ireland and the Isle of Man.

Working for local government, ALG AO members have four key functions in order to encourage the identification, recording, protection, management, interpretation and promotion of archaeological sites and monuments:

- Maintain a record of the Historic Environment Record (HER) encompassing archaeological sites, monuments and landscapes.
- Provide advice and information on the care and management of the historic environment, especially through the planning system.
- Promote the recording, interpretation and understanding of the historic environment.
- Champion the historic environment's contribution to economic development and regeneration as well as learning, leisure, tourism and local distinctiveness.

ISBN 978-0-9572452-5-9

Published by Landward Research Ltd, July 2019.

Authors: Doug Rocks-Macqueen and Ben Lewis.

Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International

Note: This licence only applies to the text and images created by the authors. Some images have different licences that should be followed. See image credits at end.

ARCHAEOLOGY in DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

Local Planning Applications

Archaeologists

74% of archaeologists employed in the UK

employs more people in the UK than 313 other sectors

5,000 archaeologists employed

Annual Contributions and Savings

Up to £1.3bn saved in delay and emergency excavation costs

contributes £218m to local economies

Local Authority archaeology services worth up to £245m in savings

£15 returned for every £1 spent on planning archaeologists

Development Management Archaeology is facilitated by 270 planning archaeologists

Misconceptions of Development Management Archaeology

Causes unnecessary delays in construction

Archaeology is never listed as a reason in surveys. Top non-archaeological reasons are:

40% poor planning

34% lack/delay in information

>10% changes to the specification

The current system is failing – National Governments are having to step in

Only 0.33% of projects are not completed due to client business failures

Impedes development

Fewer than 0.01% of planning applications have archaeological concerns used as a reason to recommend refusal

Is a cause of the housing crisis

No evidence for this.

Introduction

Archaeological work was fully incorporated as a material consideration into the planning system across the UK in the early 1990s to manage the impacts that development may have upon the historic environment. The majority of this work is undertaken on undesignated sites (not protected by listing or scheduling) in which the scale, quality and significance of the archaeological resources are often unknown fully before it is considered in the planning process. Therefore, development management archaeology plays a key role in the delivering of the nation's successful construction developments.

This report presents the results of research conducted by Landward Research Ltd for ALGAO:UK, on the archaeology sector in developmental management and its contributions in England, Scotland and Wales. It is divided into several sections: one section explores the positive impact the existing system makes on the sector and beyond. The second examines how successful the existing system is and whether it is delivering the process it was created for. The report ends with a methodological description.

What is Development Management Archaeology?

This is archaeology undertaken to meet development needs, the majority of which occur in the planning system. There are two broad major categories of archaeologists working in this area: 'commercial' archaeologists who undertake the work to discharge historic environment planning conditions, and 'local planning authority' archaeologists who review planning applications and provide advice on planning conditions. The latter are not all directly employed by local authorities, reflecting the increasing variety of emerging models of service, for example - shared services, Service Level Agreements, the Welsh Trusts and the public procurement of private contractors. The 'commercial' archaeologists are equally diverse, including private companies, charities, government bodies, sole traders, universities, museums and many others. 'Commercial archaeologists' and 'local planning authority' archaeologists are used throughout this report as shorthand terms for broad and complex groups. Data on both are presented in this report to produce a holistic view of the development management archaeology system and its contributions in England, Scotland and Wales.

Development Management Archaeology in 2017-18

525,000 planning applications submitted

England (470,000)

Scotland (26,000)

Wales (29,000)

Of these, only 21,700 planning applications had archaeological implications

England (16,000)

Scotland (3,900)

Wales (800)

2,600 predetermination investigation recommendations

England (2,200)

Scotland (300)

Wales (85)

10,000 recommendations for archaeological investigations

(Scotland and England only)

Only 55 applications were recommended for refusal in part because of preservation *in situ* needs

England 13

Scotland 31

Wales 11

The Contributions of Development Management Archaeology

Economic Contribution

£218m the direct contribution to the economy from commercial archaeology

The total estimated revenue generated by commercial archaeology in 2017-18 was £239m, of which £218m was related to development management.

£13-17m the direct contribution to the economy from local authority planning archaeology

The local planning authority archaeologists, who review planning applications and provide advice on planning conditions, contribute an estimated £13-17m per year.

Economic Contribution

Average return of £15 for every £1
spent on Local Authority Planning Archaeology

Development management archaeology is facilitated by local planning authority archaeologists. They review planning applications and provide advice on planning conditions, effectively facilitating the £218m system. The cost for those services is estimated at £13-17m per annum which means that for every pound spent on local planning authority archaeologists the local economy sees £13-17 in return from the commercial archaeologists' work, an average of £15.

Employment Contribution

74% of archaeologists are employed because of the developmental management system

In 2017-18, there were an estimated 6,800 archaeologists employed in the UK. 4,500 work in commercial archaeology, excluding those employed in non-development management projects. Local planning authority archaeologists (270), HER (Historic Environment Record) staff (100) and museum staff (150) contribute a further 500 archaeologists to the sector for a total of 5,000 (74%) archaeologists working in the development management system. The remaining archaeologists work in other capacities, like national government agencies, in public archaeology or in the education sector.

370 Local Authority and HER
archaeologists make this system possible

Employment Contribution

43rd percentile in UK employment

Archaeology, all of it, is larger than 344 other sectors in the UK. Development management archaeology employs as many or more people than 313 sectors, and falls in the 43rd percentile. Some examples of sectors that all of archaeology and development management archaeology are larger than include:

Sector	Employed
03120 : Freshwater fishing	300
79901 : Activities of tourist guides	900
01700 : Hunting, trapping and related service activities	1000
03220 : Freshwater aquaculture	1000
32200 : Manufacture of musical instruments	1000
02200 : Logging	1250
05102 : Mining of hard coal from open cast coal working	1250
24520 : Casting of steel	1500
03210 : Marine aquaculture	1750
58210 : Publishing of computer games	1750
55202 : Youth hostels	2250
20110 : Manufacture of industrial gases	3500
24510 : Casting of iron	3500
03110 : Marine fishing	4000
32300 : Manufacture of sports goods	5000
69203 : Tax consultancy	5000
85530 : Driving school activities	5000
Development Management Related Archaeologists	5000
35210 : Manufacture of gas	6000
49200 : Freight rail transport	6000
All ARCHAEOLOGISTS	6800

Economic Value

0.13% of construction spending

Total Costs in 2017-18: 0.13%

In 2017, the total purchases of goods, materials and services for the construction sector in the UK was £167,730mⁱ.

The total revenue brought in by commercial archaeology companies was £218 million for development management archaeology, 0.13% of the total purchases in the construction sector.

Stable spending

In 2007, an estimated £144m was spent on commercial archaeology, 0.14% of the overall cost of construction in the UK thenⁱⁱ.

Economic Value

Up to £1.3bn in savings through reduced delay costs
in 2017-18 alone

Development management archaeology plays a key role in delivering successful development. It can greatly reduce the delay costs incurred during construction projects, saving both the private sector, and the public, significant amounts of money.

Examining the data it was found that delays due to archaeology discovered late in the construction process can increase associated costs by 3-7x. With the current spend of £218 of per annum, archaeology in the development management system could be saving the UK up to £1.3bn per year.

Economic Value

Up to £245m in savings through local authority archaeological planning services in 2017-18

Local authority advice, provided by a variety of service models (shared services, Trusts, service level agreements *etc.*), is incredibly efficient. Under the current system, local authority services evaluate planning applications for their potential archaeological impact. When compared to alternative methods of delivery this system saved developers, both private and public, up to ¼ £billion in 2017-18.

Facilitation of the Insurance Market

“unusual and occasional situations may arise where an insurance indemnity may be required, for example delay due to discovery of archaeological objects in the ground”ⁱⁱⁱ - Chartered Institute of Insurers

Developers may insure themselves against unexpected archaeological discoveries *i.e.* delay costs, archaeological costs, cancellation costs, redesign costs, *etc.* Some large developers have this type of insurance included within their wider coverage while others obtain archaeological insurance as standalone policies. The project team interviewed all of the standalone archaeological insurance providers in the UK, which provided key insights:

- One provider has never received a claim
- Others estimate that 1 in 1000 policies are claimed on
- The archaeological insurance market could not exist without the current planning system.

The reason this sort of insurance market could not exist is because the insurance providers conduct assessments of the likelihood of claims being made. To do this they require a desk-based assessment (DBA), produced as part of the planning process. Furthermore, they need access to HERs to conduct wider research into the archaeological potential of an area. The Insurers view the HERs and their local authority staff to be ‘honest brokers’ of the relevant information they need to estimate risk.

If the current system did not exist most of the insurers do not believe that they would be able to offer such protection. Without the current system the local authority archaeologists could not support the production of competent DBAs. There would be little trust in the DBAs produced that had not been independently verified for quality, as is currently done by local authority archaeological services.

The image shows an archaeological excavation site. The ground is dark brown soil with some white mineral deposits. Several fragments of metal, likely bronze or copper, are scattered across the site. These fragments are heavily patinated with a bright green verdigris. Two scale bars are visible: one at the top and one at the bottom, both marked in centimeters. The text 'Misconceptions of Development Management Archaeology' is overlaid in the center in a bold, dark red font.

Misconceptions of Development Management Archaeology

Is the current system failing and are government bodies having to step in to finish projects?

No, only 0.33% of archaeological projects are not completed due to client business failure

The current development-led archaeology mitigation system, in place for almost 30 years, is predicated on the principle of 'the polluter pays'. That means that any work undertaken to mitigate damage done to the historic environment must be paid for by those responsible for the damage.

While successful, this system is also not without its issues. One of these issues is that if the client paying for the mitigation ceases trading then there may no longer be funding for the work. Depending on which stage of the process this takes place at, this can either have a minimal effect or could be very damaging. If it occurs before any work is undertaken, then it has almost no effect. If it occurs after a large excavation has been completed but before the completion of post-fieldwork analysis, then the cost to complete the project could be considerable or even insurmountable. In some of these occasions, the national government heritage agencies (Historic England, Cadw, Historic Environment Scotland) have stepped forward to finance the completion of the work.

These interventions both contravene the 'polluter pays' principle and drains the available funds of these organisations. If this were to occur frequently than it would represent a failure of the current system to support the management of the historic environment.

However, that is not occurring. Research conducted for this report has found that at most, there are around 70 projects per year across the whole UK that end because of client business failure. This represents 0.33% of the 21,000 planning applications with archaeological implications. These failures occur at different stages of the project, some before any archaeology has started and so the number that require government intervention is even less than 0.33%.

Does archaeology in development management impede development?

No, only 0.01% of planning applications have had archaeology included among possible reasons for rejection

In 2017-18, an estimated 55 planning applications were initially recommended for refusal because of preservation *in situ* needs. The odds of having a recommendation for refusal on preservation *in situ* grounds is therefore roughly 1 in 10,000. Even then, half of the cases in England were dismissed after appeal. Thus the odds of actually being rejected for preservation *in situ* needs is closer to 1:20,000.

Furthermore, archaeology was the sole reason for refusal in only two cases in England. This means that most of the recommendations for refusal would have occurred without archaeological considerations.

Does archaeology cause systemic delays to construction?

No Evidence has ever been presented for this.

Other than anecdotal stories, covering individual projects, there have been no data collected that shows how developmental management archaeology, in its current form, is a significant cause of delays in the construction sector.

Delays because of archaeological work is not a top concern of developers. A report by the NHBC Foundation of small house builders and developers^{iv} found their top two concerns were the 'Planning process and associated costs' and 'Availability/cost of viable land', with the 'Availability of finance' being third. The Federation of Master Builders (FMB)^v found that 'Lack of available and viable land' was their top concern, followed by a 'Lack of finance' and then 'The planning system'.

A Survey on the Costs & Reasons for Delays in Construction Industry Projects in 2017^{vi} by Cornerstone Projects Ltd noted that 85% of companies had experienced delays on recent projects; however, archaeology and/or planning conditions were not specifically identified as major reasons. The top three were:

- 40% poor planning
- 34% lack/delay in information
- 10% changes to the specification

‘Despite these risks [complex re-phasing of work, delays and escalating costs], in the UK, significant archaeology-related delays on large-scale construction and infrastructure projects are rare. Management of archaeology is enshrined in the planning process, development sites are thoroughly scoped out, often several years in advance, and archaeological teams are contracted early.’^{vii}

Does archaeology contribute to the UK's housing crisis?

Concern has been raised that the number of houses being built in the UK is not meeting the housing “need”, commonly estimated at being between 200,000 – 400,000 new homes each year, a rate which the UK has not achieved for decades.

It has been suggested that archaeology in the planning system is a potential reason for this shortfall. For example, a 2010 Department of Communities and Local Government report noted that in some cases “requests for additional information such as a flood risk assessment or an archaeological survey contributed to the time taken to determine the application”^{viii}. However, no evidence was provided to support this.

This lack of evidence is a feature of the discussions around this issue. This project team conducted a review of the major White Papers and investigations that were produced as part of the process for reading the *Neighbourhood Planning Bill 2017* (leading to the *Neighbourhood Planning Act 2017*), as well as some older publications. The results of these investigations were best articulated by Hugh Ellis, of the Town and Country Planning Association, during the Commons Committee Debate - First Sitting of the 2017 Bill:

“The short answer to your question about whether we have evidence that conditions result in delay is that **we do not.”**

Methodology

This section of the report outlines the methodologies employed to produce the results presented in the preceding sections in this report, were required. Some of the above sections contain all the necessary details *e.g.* insurance market discussions.

Development Management Archaeology in 2017-18

The data for this section relate to local planning and was provided by the national ALGAO committees (England, Scotland and Wales) for the year 2017-18. This excludes projects that fall outside the scope of local planning *i.e.* projects subject to environmental impact assessment processes, such as High Speed 2. However, there are too few projects outside of the local planning system to change the results and these numbers should be viewed as being representative of all archaeology in development management.

For Wales, the data were in the form of annual reports from each of the Welsh Trusts with 100% coverage of Wales. For Scotland and England the data were in the form of survey results of the ALGAO members in each country. These surveys did not capture every local planning authority and are just samples. The data from England was anonymised so it was impossible for the project team to estimate the totals based on those not responding. To get country wide estimations of the various data presented in this report the assumption was made that the numbers from the missing local planning authorities would be similar to those surveyed.

The number of planning applications were used as an indication of sample coverage. This was because it was available in both England and Scotland and it was related to the numbers being examined. In Scotland the responses covered 93% of planning applications submitted in that year. So the numbers presented were obtained by dividing the sample data by 93% - using the assumption those missed would have a similar profile to those sampled.

For England, the respondents to the survey had dealt with 353,288 planning applications (75% of the 470,000 submitted in 2017-18) so the England numbers were adjusted by dividing them by 75%. The original and adjusted numbers (for Scotland and England) are as follows:

Total number of planning applications with archaeological implications	Results	Adjusted
England	12,161	16,179
Scotland	3,606	3,877
Wales	821	821
Total		20,877

No. of recommendations made for Refusal for preservation <i>in situ</i>	Results	Adjusted
England	10	13
Scotland	29	31
Wales	11	11
Total		55

Archaeological investigations	Results	Adjusted
England	5,919	7,892
Scotland	2,006	2,157
Total		10,049

Number of development proposals with recommended pre-determination work	Results	Adjusted
England	1,654	2,205
Scotland	299	322
Wales	84	84
Total		2,611

Welsh Data

The data from Wales was gathered by the project team by reading through the Welsh Trust reports and pulling out the required data. This limited compatibility to only most general results. In many cases, the reports between the Welsh Trusts did not have comparable data or the definitions were not the same. For example, the pre-determination numbers from Wales are based on comparable investigation types as listed in the other country data *e.g.* geophysics. The Welsh numbers are significantly less than the Scottish ones. One would expect the numbers to be closer to 50-60% of those in Scotland if they were proportional to population sizes or the same if they were proportional to the number of planning applications. It could be that the numbers of planning applications or population are not related to archaeological planning data. A systematic survey to gather this data in the future, instead of *ad hoc* data collection, would show whether this is a collection issue or something else.

How Accurate is the Assumption of Non-Surveyed Populations?

These adjustments to the numbers are made on the assumption that those missed by the different ALGAO surveys will have similar profiles to those covered. The samples are so large, 75%+ that it is very unlikely that the unsampled population is

significantly different from the sampled population. Though because these are estimates, there is a range of potential outcomes.

To illustrate this range here is an example for applications with archaeological potential compared to the total applications received by the respondents in England *i.e.* for every one application with archaeological potential, 'x' number of planning applications had to be reviewed e.g. 1:20, 1:30. The bar graph of the English respondent organisations (ALGAO members) is below. While not quite a long tail model it is skewed towards the lower end, with some outliers.

This means that the average of those not sampled is likely to also be a low ratio. The sample covered 349,753 planning applications, with roughly 120,000 not covered by the survey. If all the remaining archaeologists had similar archaeological potential to application ratios as the lowest respondent (1 planning application with archaeology potential for every 1.43 reviewed) then there could be up to 84,089 planning applications with archaeological potential missed by the survey data ($120,247 / 1.43 = 84,089$). This is not likely. What is more likely is those not surveyed populations have similar numbers to the mean or median.

However, if the missing data is different it is unlikely to affect outcomes. Even if the non-surveyed archaeologists fell on the 25th or 75th percentile of the surveyed data, the total applications for England, Scotland and Wales would only range between 19,000 to 25,000 which means that between 3.6% and 4.8% of the applications would have archaeological potential – so that would not even represent a 1% difference in the total.

Because of these ranges in estimates we are not able to say precisely that there were 20,877 applications with archaeology implications. So as to not mislead readers into thinking these numbers are 100% precise, all of the headline figures are rounded. It is hoped that this gives the impression that these numbers are not precise.

Data Comparability

The different ALGAO surveys asked questions in slightly different forms. The project team did our best to align them. The follow table outlines how the questions were aligned.

Data	England	Scotland
Planning applications reviewed	Total number of planning applications submitted in 2017/18 for the local authorities advised District/Borough/Unitary and/or County Matter (NB this is ALL applications, regardless of archaeological implications, and inclusive of those applications which may apply to Q23 (below).	Total number of planning determinations made by the local authorities advised (April 2017-March 2018)
With archaeological potential	Total number of planning applications with archaeological implications: This should include all proposals for which assessment or mitigation recommendations were made.	Following the initial appraisal, what is the number of proposals with archaeological implications (i.e. require some form of archaeological mitigation) in each of the following categories:
Predetermination investigations recommendations	Total number of development proposals for which you have recommended any pre-determination field evaluation (pre-submission and all types of field	Number of development proposals for which you have recommended pre-determination (or equivalent for proposals such as utilities which don't fall within the

Data	England	Scotland
	evaluation) Please do not count historic building assessments or Strategic Housing Land Availability Assessments as these are covered separately.	planning system) archaeological work (<i>i.e.</i> a desk-based assessment, field evaluation, walkover survey)
Recommendations for archaeological investigations	<p>Total number of planning applications where a condition was recommended for below-ground archaeology</p> <p>Total number of planning applications where a condition was recommended for historic building recording. (Advice on historic buildings has been included to obtain an overview of which services are providing such advice and how frequent it is. Where below-ground and historic building assessment have been recommended for the same application, please count separately)</p>	<p>Number of curatorial instructions issued for the following types of work: This question refers to briefs – and also specifications/planning recommendation letters – issued by historic environment services. The split questions are to obtain figures on the number and proportion of full excavation briefs – as opposed to evaluation. The question on historic buildings should include briefs which also have below ground archaeological investigation included within them. It would be useful if the number of these could also be included to avoid double counting.</p>
Recommendation for refusal b/c of preservation <i>in situ</i>	In how many refusals was archaeology given as a reason because of the presence of remains requiring preservation <i>in situ</i> ?	<p>Number of known instances for which archaeology was an issue by being a reason for refusal because of: The presence of remains requiring preservation <i>in situ</i></p>

Economic Contribution

The data for commercial archaeology comes from the most recent *State of the Archaeological Market*^{ix}, conducted by Landward Research Ltd on behalf of CIFA, FAME and Historic England. This survey estimated that, in financial year 2017-18, the commercial archaeological sector contributed £239m to the UK economy. Of that

amount 91.4% was from development control related events (£218m). 'Other research and public archaeology' (4.5%) and 'community projects and HLF' (4.1%) made up the remainder of the funding for commercial archaeology (£21m).

For the estimate of local authority archaeologists' contribution to the economy, the numbers of such archaeologists and their average salaries were used. The data provided by ALGAO included staffing numbers. For Scotland, there were 24.1 full-time-equivalent staff. There are at least three non-ALGAO members in Scotland for a total number of 27^x. This includes temporary staff, administrative support and strategic/management input covers.

For England, data was provided on a more nuanced level include different values for HER, archaeology and other staff:

England:	HER	Archaeological planning / conservation advice	Conservation Officers	Education /outreach /community engagement	Other
Current Staff	56.05	81.7	29.9	15.2	28.4

Again, the assumption was made that staffing levels of those not surveyed will be similar to those that were surveyed. Assuming that the coverage of 75% of planning applications is similar to staffing levels then the total staff numbers were divided by 75%. Results are as follows:

Staff Type	Actual	Estimated
HER (inc. EUS, HLC)	63.8	85.07
Archaeological planning/conservation advice	106.75	142.33
Conservation Officers	38.9	51.87
Education/outreach/community engagement	16.5	22.00
Other (including PAS, admin/management time)	32.25	43.00
Vacant posts	20.45	27.27

There were no numbers available for Wales, so it was assumed there was a similar number of staff to the total in Scotland who process a comparable number of planning applications.

Using this methodology it is estimated that there are 270 archaeologists working in archaeological planning and HER roles. As with the other numbers in this report there is a potential range in results. The total number of people working in archaeology in local authorities is closer to 380 if other positions such as public engagement, Portable Antiquities Scheme, *etc.* are included.

The *Profiling the Profession* report^{xi} found that the average wage for planning positions was £31,000 and £25,000 for HER officers. Multiplying these ranges by the estimated 270 archaeologists working in local authorities and then doubling this to include overheads produces a range of costs from £13.5-16.7m.

This value for local authority archaeologists was then compared with the value of commercial archaeology to get the £1:£15 ratio.

Employment Contribution

The estimate for commercial archaeology numbers comes from the *State of the Archaeological Market*^{xii}. The full number of commercial archaeologists is estimated to be c. 5000. However, only 91% of their paid work comes from development management so that number was multiplied by 91% to get the number of commercial archaeologists. The numbers for local authority advice and planning archaeologists comes from the previously mentioned methodology. The number of Museum Archaeologists comes from the *Profiling the Profession* report^{xiii}. These are included because there are very few research-only archaeologists in museums. Most are curating the finds from development management archaeology. It is unlikely that many of those archaeological jobs would exist if they did not have to manage the large collections produced by development management archaeology.

The Office of National Statistics *Business Register and Employment Survey* tracks the number of people employed by sectors, 731 of them, in the UK. These data were used to determine which sectors archaeology was bigger and smaller than.

Economical Value

Construction cost data is discussed in that section and the cost of commercial archaeology uses the above-mentioned numbers.

Delay Savings

Development management archaeological services play a key advisory and management role in identifying potential impacts and delivering successful development. One way it does this is through the reduction in delays. Identifying archaeology early in the construction process can reduce or eliminate delays to the project which can result in significant savings. Research by the City of London in 2007 identified the many ways delays, because of not properly addressing archaeological issues, can increase development costs^{xiv}:

- Real example - Accelerated work procedures costing £250,000
- Real example - Weekly *damages* of £100,000 due to delay in demolition contract

- Delays to *piling* (commonly the first activity after archaeology) can be ‘particularly costly’
- Letting losses – delays mean rents are not collected
- Hypothetical example: £100 million development cost 85% served by debt finance, interest could run as high as £8.5m per year.

‘The risks of not considering archaeology early within a planned development can include delays to the work programme, costly redesign work, work coming to a halt, long-term reputational damage if things go wrong’^{xv}

By including archaeology in the planning system and setting appropriate mitigation strategies to meet the conditions of the planning authorities, developers are saved from incurring costs through delays that can harm their bottom line and the viability of their projects. To estimate the savings that this system provides, the project team had to determine how much delays would cost developers in the old “pre-planning” system when archaeology was often not integral to the planning process and usually discovered late in project development. However, there are no data on exactly how much such delays cost developers.

The project team attempted to investigate a method for developing units of cost for delays to a development as a direct result of archaeological work. This was intended to generate indicators on a smaller scale than the scenarios described in the City of London report quoted above, such as a hypothetical development of 200 homes, delayed for eight weeks. However, after contacting many construction firms^{xvi} it was found that this was not possible to get useable figures; such a wide range of variables go into construction costs, from materials to design to financing and – critically – at what stage in the process the delays occurred in the construction process, meaning it was not possible to construct a micro-example of costs due to delays. Therefore Esgeneralisations, it was determined, could not be made.

Focus then turned to estimating macro-costs. Examples were found of projects that either had price overruns because of the discovery of archaeology or in which more extreme methods of work were undertaken to complete and finish the project faster. Two examples are presented as case studies and are examined next.

Case Study 1: Northern Ireland Roads Contract

In 2007, the Northern Ireland Roads Service contracted Amey Lagan Roads to construct 78 miles of motorway and improvements across three scheme sites for £255m^{xvii}. Prior to construction, the Roads Service had conducted £2.6m of archaeological surveys over a seven-year period to mitigate risks. Had no extra work been needed, this would have amounted to 1% of total construction costs for the Road Service.

However, once construction started, substantial archaeological deposits were found at sites in Counties Down and Tyrone and the work was delayed. The contractor initially asked for an additional £33.7m – representing £3.8m in further archaeological consultation, £4m in lost overheads and profit, and the remainder for all other impacts on the schemes as a result of the delay^{xviii}. The contract between the two parties stipulated that the contractor was liable for the cost of ‘foreseeable’ archaeology and the Roads Service was liable for ‘unforeseeable’ archaeology. The Road Services eventually paid the contractor £17.22m for the delays, equal to 7.2% of the Service’s overall construction budget.

The Northern Ireland Audit Agency investigated the settlement and concluded that the Road Services had done all it could to eliminate the risks of ‘unforeseen archaeology’. Recommendations arising from the case included the tightening of the definition of ‘unforeseeable archaeology’, the involvement of the Northern Ireland Environment Agency on a scheme-by-scheme basis in ‘archaeologically sensitive’ areas, and the use of trial-trenching as a method to better understand potential archaeological risks^{xix}.

Case Study 2: The Rose to the Curtain Theatre

The discovery of two Elizabethan theatres known to have staged Shakespeare’s works 30 years apart demonstrate how developers’ engagement with archaeological discoveries had changed.

In 1989, the discovery and potential destruction of The Rose theatre (built 1587) during re-development on London’s Bankside sparked a high-profile campaign with celebrity involvement.^{xx} The campaign contributed to the introduction of *Planning Policy Guidance 16: Archaeology and Planning* (PPG16) in 1990, making archaeology a material consideration in the planning process.^{xxi} The re-development work was altered after construction had begun, at the cost of £11 million, to preserve the theatre beneath.

In contrast, exploratory investigation by the Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) in 2012 uncovered the remains of the Curtain Theatre in Shoreditch.^{xxii} Built a decade before *The Rose*, the Curtain Theatre had housed performances of Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet* as well as the works of Ben Jonson. Project developers Plough Yard Developments submitted a planning application in 2013 that was informed by the site's history and allowed for the preservation of the important remains. Backed by The Shakespeare Globe Theatre Trust and English Heritage, the development would include a 40-storey tower block accompanied by a visitor centre, public performance space and the preservation of The Curtain Theatre under a glass enclosure.^{xxiii}

The development, now called 'The Stage', "places the theatre and its archaeology front and centre in visitors' and users' experiences". The developer has continued to work closely with MOLA to preserve the theatre's remains through further excavations in 2016, opening a visitor centre and providing a programme of community events.^{xxiv}

Since *The Rose* was uncovered, developers have had the opportunity to engage with archaeology early and make it an active part of a project's design, ensuring that unique characters of historic environment are identified and enhanced – while also saving millions in redevelopment and delay costs.

"For a major development... archaeological costs, in the form of payments to archaeologists, attendance labour, assistance in kind and enabling works are likely to cost between 1% and 3% of a total construction cost where major significant archaeology survives. The archaeological cost exceeds 3% only in very rare circumstances but more frequently it is significantly less than 1%. Additional costs in excess of agreed contract sums are rarely claimed. In terms of a total development cost the percentage will be significantly smaller."^{xxv}

Estimated savings

1% is the accepted baseline for costs in the current system. The 7.2% of total project costs caused by archaeology related delays, as discussed in the Northern Ireland Roads case study, was the highest total project costs identified during our research. There are several examples of pre-contemporary archaeological planning practice projects in the 1980s that might be higher. 85 Queen Victoria Street (Huggin Hill Baths) in the City of London was £5 million (£3 million from interest charges) and the Rose Theatre excavation discussed above (in Southwark) cost an estimated £11 million, with claims that £10 million of that was in redesign as construction had already started. The cost of changes in later stages of projects causes costs to rise exponentially. However, the project team were not able to locate information on total project costs so we cannot present estimates of what these changes represent in percentage terms. This means that failure to consider archaeology appropriately could potentially increase costs seven-fold through delays. If the current levels of spending of £218m is multiplied by seven - to £1.5bn - this represents a potential saving of £1.3bn.

Maximum Potential Savings

The maximum rate of savings assumes that all archaeological projects would lead to higher costs if the archaeological matters are not addressed early in project planning. This would not be the case for investigations that return negative results *i.e.* no archaeological remains, or for projects with minimal findings. For example, if during a watching brief a small pit was discovered it might be excavated and recorded by the archaeologists during a watching brief phase. This could then be followed by the planning archaeologists determining that no additional work would be required. Unfortunately, while there are data on how many investigations take place, there are no data on the percentage of those investigations that result in negative results or minimal additional archaeological work. We need to know how many projects find significant archaeological resources to be able to more accurately estimate the savings. Until those data are available, the £1.3bn figure has to be seen as maximum of a potential range.

So what? Why not ignore the archaeology?

It could be argued that these savings in delays would not occur if archaeology was simply ignored. That is not a legal option. The United Kingdom is a signatory to the Valletta Treaty, a legally binding treaty through the Council of Europe that mandates consideration of archaeology in the planning process and to modify development plans if they adversely affect archaeological resources. This is not a European Union (EU) treaty and will not be affected by the UK possible leaving the EU. Through international treaties the UK has to legally have these considerations.

Moreover, as demonstrated in the case study of the Rose Theatre local communities can be motivated to try to stop the destruction of archaeological remains.

Attempting to avoid archaeological work is likely to result in later delays and thus higher costs. This system has to legally exist, but it is an efficient system that is less costly than the alternative of waiting till the last possible moment to address archaeological resources.

Estimated current savings by having 'in-house' archaeological services

Under the current system, local curatorial services evaluate planning applications for potential archaeological impact. Only a small percentage (4%) of these 525,000 planning applications are deemed to require further work. This local authority advice provided by a variety of service models both direct and indirect (shared services, Trusts, service level agreements *etc.*) is incredibly efficient.

The UK is legally obliged to have archaeology in the planning system but the Valletta Treaty is not prescriptive in terms of how this should be accomplished. The current system, with local authority archaeologists reviewing and advising on planning applications is not the only system to accomplish this. However, if the current system were not in place there are only a limited number of methods that could replace it; some of them are:

1. Implement a purely reactive model of on-site discovery and reporting – politically unacceptable and would contradict current UK national and local planning, heritage and environmental policy. This is a method that has been tried in the past and failed. It costs developers significantly more money and throws out all of the savings discussed above with mitigating delays. This method greatly increases the risks to developers of harming both their bottom-line and even the viability of their projects.

2a. Have developers self-certify the archaeological needs of their application. This runs into several risks and problems. One is that developers typically do not have the skills and knowledge to conduct archaeological evaluations. Moreover, such a system would suffer from a classic problem of asymmetrical information, leaving certain developers potentially paying for mitigation while those that self-certified that no archaeological work is needed would pay nothing, giving the latter a commercial advantage. This would encourage all developers to initially self-certify that no archaeology exists on their sites. However, as archaeological remains might indeed be present, this would ultimately lead to higher costs through delays.

2b. Have external evaluations conducted by archaeologists to certify whether work is or is not needed. This has an advantage over self-certification in that the archaeologist would be qualified to evaluate the site's archaeological potential. This would be a commercial market system in which developers would seek out archaeologists to certify their needs. Again, there is great potential for abuse as

developers would be under pressure to find archaeologists who tend to certify that there are no archaeological needs in order to save themselves money further along in the process. Conversely, archaeologists would be under pressure in this market system to attract clients – possibly by building a reputation for saving them money *i.e.* by certifying ‘no’. It may also be that people without any archaeological knowledge could offer these certificates, and so these would likely be of poor quality. These poor-quality certifications would lead to the same issues of unknown archaeology being discovered late in the process – and so to increasing costs. It would also likely lead to legal disputes over who is to blame for delay and who is responsible for meeting the increased costs.

These routes lead to the same outcome – late identification and archaeological resources and higher costs. To avoid this, local planning officers could require a detailed report outlining whether archaeological work is required. This would allow them to better assess the quality of the advice given to the developer and potentially refuse those that do not provide sufficient evidence. For the purposes of this report we will refer to these reports as ‘Desk-based Planning Assessments’ (an extension of the current Desk Based Assessment style report that also provides the archaeological advice currently provided by local planning archaeologists). This would require all planning applications to provide a DBPA provided by suppliers in the marketplace.

The project team sampled current commercial providers of desk-based assessments to estimate what the costs would be to cover all planning applications with DBPAs. Prices vary greatly, depending upon the size of the development, location of the project and contractors. The lowest, very basic price, for a small, simple development, was £500. At this rate, the cost to the construction sector for DBPAs would have been a minimum of £262.5m in 2017-18.

Desk-based Planning Assessments (DBPA) could potentially cost less than full Desk-based Assessments (DBAs). Archaeologists could find ways to streamline the process but at a minimum they would have to present what they found in their search of the local Historic Environment Record (HER). In some places, the access and searching costs for a local HER is £100. Not all HERs charge for access and searches. Thus not all would incur this cost but there are costs in time and so, for this exercise, we assume an average of £100. Even assuming an ‘at cost’ rate of an average of £100 per DBPA the cost would still be £53m per year.

This cost is based on the current system where some of the costs to maintain an HER, in most cases, are met from a form of cross-subsidy from the planning service as the HER is an essential tool for Planning Archaeologists. If that system changes or the Planning Archaeologist role disappears, then commercial search charges might have

to radically increase in order to achieve full cost recovery. It may be that costs would actually increase above the estimated £500 per DBPA.

As outlined in other sections of this methodology, the estimated cost of local authority archaeologists and HER officers is between £13-17m. This is significantly less than the minimum estimated cost of £262.5 million for the possible system outlined above. Essentially, the current system allows Local Authority archaeologists to consult the HER and make initial appraisals of the c.525,000 planning applications which often avert the need for full desk-based assessments, as only 4% really require more investigations, at a fraction of the cost.

However, this only works because of trust and independent reviews. They are not dependent on pleasing clients by finding a particular outcome. Any system looking to replace this will incur significant increases in costs in order to be able to mitigate the problems of not having trust and independence. The current system might be the most cost-effective method there is.

Client Failure

To obtain data on the number of projects where clients have collapsed before the project was completed, in the autumn of 2018, Landward Research Ltd surveyed employers in commercial archaeology as part of the recent *State of the Archaeological Market*^{xxvi} survey and included a question to gather these data: 'In the year ending 31st March 2018, how many of your projects were not completed because of a client suffering business failure?'

Of the 51 respondents to the survey, 12 confirmed at least one incidence of client business failure - 7 had one client fail, 4 had two clients fail and 1 had three clients fail for a total of 18 failures. The respondents represent the employers of 26.6% of archaeologists in the commercial sector, who secured 25.4% of the sector's annual turnover. Extrapolating this out to the rest of the sector produces an estimate for the number of archaeological projects not being completed because of client business failure of around 70 projects per year across the whole UK.

This represents 0.33% of the 21,000 planning applications with archaeological implications. These could include projects where work never started. Conditions might have been set but the project then collapsed before any archaeological work ever got underway. Regardless of when the projects fail, 0.33% does not represent a failure of the system. Evidence, in the form of comments on the survey, indicated some of these failures were the result of the liquidation of Carillion in 2018 and would indicate that the rate was unusually high in 2017-18 (the year the data were collected).

This is a sample survey, but 25% coverage of the sector means that at a 99% confidence level the margin of error is $\pm 3\%$.

Does archaeology in development management impede development?

As with other data provided by ALGAO these numbers were adjusted to account for those missed by the survey.

Does archaeology cause systemic delays to construction?

Systematic research was conducted, and the only data found is presented in the text. Given that archaeological work is only involved in less than 4% of planning applications it is not surprising that it is not considered a major delay.

Does the cost of archaeology contribute significantly to the UK's housing crisis?

We reviewed all of the evidence about delays presented in various Bills and White Papers over the last few years. This is what we found in terms of comments on it and the fact that there is no supporting data:

Fixing our broken housing market (2017)^{xxvii}

Building Homes Faster

‘unnecessary delays caused by planning conditions’ (p.36)

‘Local authorities and developers have told us about a range of issues that slow down the building of new homes, such as local planning authority capacity to handle applications (1); too many applications going to appeal; the time taken to discharge planning conditions or address planning obligations; a lack of infrastructure; problems securing the necessary utility connections; excessive bureaucracy in protecting species like great crested newts; and skills shortages.’

Tackling unnecessary delays caused by planning conditions

2.26 We will tackle unnecessary delays caused by planning conditions by taking forward proposals, through the Neighbourhood Planning Bill, to allow the Secretary of State to prohibit conditions that do not meet the national policy tests, and to ensure that pre-commencement conditions can only be used with the agreement of the applicant. We introduced a new deemed discharge mechanism for planning conditions in 2015 and we are keen to hear more from developers, local authorities and other interested parties about how this is working and if we can streamline the process further.

A strategic approach to the habitat management of protected species

2.27 House-builders have identified the licensing system for protected species such as great crested newts as a significant impediment to timely housing delivery.

Natural England and Woking Borough Council have piloted a new strategic approach which streamlines the licensing system for managing great crested newts – the species which particularly affects development. The Government will roll out this approach to help other local authorities speed up the delivery of housing and other development. (p.48)

Neighbourhood Planning Bill 2017

First Reading Neighbourhood Planning Bill^{xxviii} – unavailable, website issue

Second Reading Neighbourhood Planning Bill^{xxix}

Theresa Pearce (Lab Shadow SoS): “London Councils has said that there is little robust evidence to suggest that the current planning conditions system has led to an under-supply of housing... I am yet to see firm statistical evidence of how much pre-commencement planning conditions restrict building”. Complained prevalence of anecdotal evidence.

Gavin Barwell (Con Minister for Housing and Planning): “The DCN (District Councils Network) has acknowledged that the discharge of planning conditions can be an actor on slow decision making and supports the government in seeking to address conditions.”

DCN clarified that “slowness of statutory consultee responses and the impact this is having in timely decision making which can influence significantly the speed at which the conditions are discharged^{xxx}”

GB: “The consultation paper states: “This measure will not restrict the ability of local planning authority to propose pre-commencement conditions that may be necessary—for example, conditions in relation to archaeological investigations or wildlife surveys. “So there is protection there”.

GB: “A survey of small and medium-sized builders carried out by the National House Building Council reported that 34% of them were concerned about the time to clear conditions and 29% of them were concerned about the extent of those conditions, so there is real evidence of concern on that issue.”

His source: NHBC Foundation (2014), *Improving the prospects for small house builders and developers^{xxxi}*, pp. 5.

More recently: NHBC Foundation(2017), *Small house builders and developers: Current challenges to growth^{xxxii}*, pp.19

Anecdotal evidence added by:

Geoffrey Clifton-Brown (Con) “over-zealous pre-commencement conditions”

Robert Neill (Con) “24 conditions, 14 of them pre-commencement... A number of them in effect duplicated building regulation requirements... regulations on fuel conservation”

Chris Philip (Con) “the notorious cases of bat and newt studies... wretched creature”

Oliver Letwin (Con) “absurd pre-commencement conditions”

Kevin Hollinrake (Con): “a landscape scheme before starting on the development itself, as a pre-commencement condition”

“Bats and newts” a key catchphrase.

Caution against the bill:

Roberta-Blackman-Woods (Lab) “I have a list from a development taking place in my constituency and I cannot see what is wrong with any of these conditions”

Theresa Villiers (Con) “announcement of the Bill in the Queen’s Speech indicated that obligations to carry out archaeological and wildlife surveys would be “swept away”.

TP: “It is not pre-commencement planning conditions that slow planning consent, but the chronic underfunding of local planning authorities.”

RN: “The Welsh Assembly Government have put the historic environmental record on a statutory footing. It might be useful to do that here so that local heritage information is available. That would avoid the risk of something being thrown up that delays the process after a good deal of investment has taken place.

Commons Committee Debate: First Sitting^{xxxiii}

BPF Roy Kinnock: Killian Pretty Review^{xxxiv} identified an average of eight conditions, now could “range up to as many as 22” [however according to NHBC (2017): 7% would have 21-30 conditions]

FMB Andrew Dixon: “signing off of planning conditions came at No. 2 out of six, I think, just behind the under-resourcing of local planning departments”^{xxxv}

“Under-resourcing is a major issue that causes numerous hold-ups within the system, and we think it is one of the drivers behind the excessive use of conditions”

HBF Andrew Whitaker: “It’s very much a chicken-and egg situation. If local authorities do not put enough resources into determining a planning application, the temptation is—rather lazily, in my opinion—to deal with everything via condition, rather than as part of the primary application. If authorities focused their resources on what needed to be done as part of the application, they would need to condition less”

(Historic England) Duncan Wilson: “Essentially, we believe the current system works quite well. We understand that developers need certainty and the system provides for conditions relating to investigation of sensitive sites. Only about 2% of planning applications are covered by these archaeological pre-commencement conditions.”

“We think, on balance, the system as it exists works pretty well for developers because it is based on an investigation of what is actually there and an assessment of the risks. That relies on local authority expertise and resources to help make that assessment, and we [HE] have our part to play in that too.”

(Town and Country Planning Association) Hugh Ellis: “The short answer to your question about whether we have evidence that conditions result in delay is that we do not. What we do have is a growing concern that planning has to strike the right balance between the efficiency of the system for applicants and outcomes for people.”

Gavin Barwell: “in the year to 30 June, this country granted a record number of planning applications for housing, but that there is a gap between the planning permissions we are granting and homes being built out. If you do not think planning conditions are part of the problem—I would certainly say they are not the sole problem”

Commons Committee Debate: Fifth Sitting^{xxxvi}

Roberta Blackman-Wood (Lab): Little evidence provided. “The BPF at least helpfully referred to a survey; the HBF admitted that it was relying more or less on anecdotes from builders ... We heard in oral evidence the opinion of some of the volume house builders, although we did not get from the HBF any examples of what types of conditions were proving problematic ... I say that because nobody else seems to have identified pre-commencement conditions as a problem, but clearly the Minister thinks they are and some of his colleagues seem to think they are.”

Helen Hayes “officers are currently using pre-commencement conditions because they are simply unable to resolve every aspect of the planning application before the deadline for making a decision”

GB: “I want to pick up on three specific examples that we were given of pre-commencement conditions, one of which may help to provide my right hon. Friend the Member for Chipping Barnet with the reassurance she sought. I thought that the three examples delineated very well the difference between the two sides of the Committee on this issue. One example related to archaeological concerns. Clearly it is entirely appropriate to address those through a pre-commencement condition. If there are concerns that the moment someone gets on site and starts to do

groundworks they will destroy a key archaeological site, the issue has to be dealt with by a pre-commencement procedure.

The other examples concerned the use of materials and landscaping. I, and I am sure all members of the Committee, would accept that those issues are legitimate ones that communities would want to address through the planning process. However, I do not accept that they must be dealt with before a single thing can be done on site, as the development begins to get under way. There is no reason why they cannot be dealt with during the process.”

Lords Committee Debate: First Sitting^{xxxvii}

Reference to the HBF report: Playgrounds

Reference to the NHBC 34%/29% Stat (see above)

Lord Stunell (LD): The noble Lord, Lord Young, produced the outstandingly shocking news that developers do not like planning applications. I would not have thought it difficult to get a developer to write a letter to say, “I do not like planning conditions”, but developers are not always the best judge of what makes a sensible planning condition. A developer in a rush may find a pre-commencement planning condition that says, “You must carry out a proper archaeological survey” as nothing but a waste of time and money—it is only a pile of old stones. If a local authority cannot impose a pre-commencement condition relating to archaeological investigation as a result of some ministerial direction—well, I am sure that the Minister will reassure us that this is not the intention. He will say, I predict, that archaeology will still be permitted to be set as a pre-commencement condition, which I am pleased about. I could ask a whole lot of other questions and I am sure that he would say exactly the same to all of them: “The Government have no intention of introducing regulations”.

Cutting Red Tape: Review of house building (HM Government) (2017)^{xxxviii}

“There was a substantial consensus amongst house builders that the six policy tests in the National Planning Policy Framework for the implementation of planning conditions are not being properly practised by Local Planning Authorities. They believed that too many unnecessary planning conditions are imposed and they can take too long to be discharged.” (p.4)

Methodology: 41 targeted interviews and received 133 comments via the Cutting Red Tape website. We also received a number of detailed emailed submissions from key interest groups.

“One house builder reported the cost of dealing with great crested newts in 2013 at an average of £2,261.55 per newt relocated. This took into account consultant fees, land purchase for the relocated newts and contracting costs for the physical

relocation. Another large builder reported a sum of £500,000 spent on one site where just five newts were found.” (p.5)

Building More Homes (2016)^{xxxix}

“Delays in the planning system...

The imposition of planning conditions and delays certifying compliance with these conditions.

David Orr from the National Housing Federation stated that in his experience it could be a year after planning consent was granted “before you can actually lay a brick”.

Jennie Daly (Taylor Wimpey): 415 sites with detailed planning permission, 371 already on site and building, 34 gearing up to start immediately, 8 waiting for planning conditions to be discharged, 2 sites with viability issues. Question is about land banking and the use of Taylor Wimpey’s short-term pipeline of 45 sites. Describes the 2 unviable sites as ‘such a small level that it is below the level of statistical importance or relevance’.

Dame Kate Barber: “Why do you not get on the site the day after the planning permission? Generally, you are waiting for your planning conditions to be cleared. At the moment, one of the issues is that local authorities have stripped their staff down so much that you can sometimes wait two or three months to get your planning permission cleared”

David Orr: “local authority planning departments are under resourced and there is also a lack of focus on delivery post-consent. Between us, we need to sharpen up that post-consent part of the process; it can often take a year before you can actually lay a brick after consent.”

Implementation of planning changes: technical consultation. Summary of Responses (2017)^{xi}

“ Many respondents asked for further clarity about who would deal with various steps in the planning process, such as pre-application advice, appeals and discharge of conditions.” (pp.21)

“On farmshops, the main issues raised related to planning conditions which were felt to be unreasonable, such as a high percentage of home-grown produce being placed on the sale of goods and opening hours excluding weekends and Bank Holidays. Some respondents raised issues related to transport and highways considerations, due to the increase in vehicle movements.” (pp.39)

Previous Government (2010-2015 Coalition)

Building regulations as a delay in housebuilding^{xli}

Laying the Foundations: A Housing Strategy for England (2011)^{xlii}

“We will encourage action on stalled development by allowing developers to require local authorities to reconsider those S106 agreements agreed in more prosperous market conditions prior to April 2010.” (pp.9)

Benchmarking the costs to applicants of submitting a planning application (2010)^{xliii}

“Of those that were determined out of time, applicants attributed the extra cost to further derivations of design required by the LPA and the extra negotiations required with officers to determine the application. In some cases, requests for additional information such as a flood risk assessment or an archaeological survey contributed to the time taken to determine the application.” (pp.39)

“where conditions had been discharged, the applicant highlighted that he felt that one particular condition was onerous and overly costly to discharge: a high proportion of the overall costs was paid to a landscaping consultant to prepare and submit a detailed landscape management plan.” (pp.39)

Killian Pretty Review (2008)^{xliiv}

“Other concerns include that Government targets only account for the part of the overall planning journey occupied by processing the applications. Also, there is little incentive to continue processing an application expeditiously if it has missed a target, a tendency to use conditions for unresolved issues (within the deadline, instead of negotiating further and missing the deadline), and a lack of monitoring or discharging of conditions, since authorities are focused solely on processing applications”. (pp.127)

Recommendation 6: improve the approach to planning conditions, unnecessary conditions are avoided and process of discharging is clearer and more efficient. Case study research: more conditions are now being attached.

On average 8 conditions, as many as 22 (pp. 74).

Circular 11/95^{xlv} Six Tests: conditions must be necessary; relevant to planning; relevant to the development; enforceable; precise; reasonable in all other respects.

‘A one-off CLG survey in 2006 indicated that these so-called section 106 agreements are responsible for at least 50% of the delays that can occur with processing major developments’ (pp.12 – unable to find this source, not referenced)

Single year

The contribution varies year-by-year as the commercial numbers fluctuate. Thus these calculations and others regarding employment and economic contribution

should be viewed as the results of a single year. If these reports were to be run annually the results would change.

Progressive Enhancement of Research

The results presented in this report were made with the best data available. Several deficiencies in our data and methods have already been identified e.g. savings likely a maximum. This means that future research with better datasets are likely to refine and improve the precision of these numbers.

In the process of conducting this research the project team identified several areas where research could improve the precision of the results:

- Knowing where in the process projects end because of client business failure would refine the number of projects that require national governments to step in.
- Knowing the number of archaeological investigations that result in positive finds + the costs of such projects would allow for refinement of the money saved by developers.

We hope further research will provide this information and refine the results of this report.

Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland is not included in these surveys as ALGAO does not have data for Northern Ireland. In terms of other numbers, which are UK wide, e.g. the commercial archaeology data, it might affect the results slightly. The *State of the Archaeological Market* does track the registered location of a business but not the country its funding comes from. Without being able to separate out the numbers the commercial archaeology numbers include Northern Ireland, but the local authority archaeology numbers do not. However, it is not likely the inclusion or exclusion of these data would significantly change the results.

For example, assuming that work is proportional to populations then the spend and number of commercial archaeologists would need to be reduced by 2.8%. So the total number of commercial archaeologists would fall by 100. Though but given the above-mentioned range in possible numbers it is in the margin for error. The possible numbers are just too small to affect the outcomes.

Image Credits

In order of appearance in the report:

Excavation at Flodden Wall © John Lawson

Walkover survey at Stonehenge: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/12833341844/>

Geophysical Survey 9: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/2339489847/>

Geophysical Survey 7: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC 2.0

<https://flic.kr/p/4yJuPB>

Jon Egging Blue Skies programme: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/35155122300/>

Watching Brief 3: Wessex Archaeology. CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/352706545/>

Robert Brooks and Mike Feider, Suffolk County Council archaeology service, oversee an exploratory archaeological: US government – public domain

<https://www.mildenhall.af.mil/News/Photos/igphoto/2000378987/>

Two members of the Suffolk County Council Archaeology Service use trowels, brushes and hand shovels to remove the soil and debris around skeletons found in October 2010 in Washington Square: US Government – Public Domain

<https://www.mildenhall.af.mil/News/Photos/igphoto/2000309397/>

Iris wreck in NW Skye: Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/26610951691/>

CLE_1066: Colleen Morgan CC BY 2.0

<https://flic.kr/p/nmFmZs>

Sheffield Castle excavations: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC 2.0

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/43808778834/>

Volunteers learning to use a Total Station Theodolite (TST) at St Georges Church, Portland: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC 2.0

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/6880439285/>

Crossrail archaeology dig. Matt Brown CC-BY

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/londonmatt/17087614179>

Recording a Neolithic pit: Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/40129688944/>

Kilwinning abbey dig: John Loney CC BY

<https://flic.kr/p/aYpwke>

Roof beams 1: Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/852391506/>

Driffield Hoard in situ 3: The Portable Antiquities Scheme/ The Trustees of the British Museum CC BY 2.0

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Driffield Hoard in situ 3.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Driffield_Hoard_in_situ_3.jpg)

Training session for Bath Abbey volunteers: Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/44203154925/>

DOR-E2A223 Piddletrenthide Hoard being excavated in the BM lab: The Portable Antiquities Scheme/ The Trustees of the British Museum CC BY 2.0

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/finds/38846592461/>

X-ray: Wessex Archaeology CC BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/9947884963/>

Printing the past: 3-D archaeology and the first Americans: Bureau of Land Management Oregon and Washington Public Domain.

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/blmoregon/33296043631>

John Sims, an archaeologist with the Suffolk County Council Archaeological Service, removes one of the arm bones from a skeleton to be placed in a bag: US government - Public domain

Battersea Power Station And Chelsea Bridge Night: Laurence Mackman CC BY-SA 4.0

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Battersea Power Station And Chelsea B ridge Night.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Battersea_Power_Station_And_Chelsea_Bridge_Night.jpg)

Romano-British pottery kiln: Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/38824153695/>

Romano-British Dropped Flanged Bowl (view 2): Wessex Archaeology CC-BY-NC

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/wessexarchaeology/44078048110/in/photostream/>

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/constructionindustry/datasets/outputintheconstructionindustry>

ⁱⁱHinton, P., & Jennings, D., 2007 Quality management of archaeology in Great Britain: present practice and future challenges, in Willems, W., & Van Dries, M., (eds.) *Quality management in archaeology*: 100-112. Oxford: Oxbow Books.

ⁱⁱⁱ<https://www.cii.co.uk/knowledge/claims/articles/insurance-requirements-in-construction-contracts/6959>

^{iv}https://www.nhbcfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/NF76_WEB.pdf

^v<https://www.fmb.org.uk/media/35090/fmb-house-builders-survey-2017.pdf>

^{vi}<https://www.cornerstoneprojects.co.uk/index.php/delays-in-construction-projects/>

^{vii}Underground Resistance, Stephen Cousins (2016) in RICS Modus: The Ruined Issue (26 Oct 2016)

<https://www.rics.org/uk/news-insight/publications/modus/the-ruined-issue/>

^{viii}DCLG. 2010. Benchmarking the costs to applicants of submitting a planning application.

<https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919132719/http://www.communities.gov.uk/documents/planningandbuilding/pdf/benchmarkingcostsapplication.pdf>

^{ix}Aitchison, K., 2019. State of the Archaeological Market 2017-18, Landward Research Ltd.

<https://landward.eu/blog/archaeological-market-survey-2017-18/>

^xScotland has a small enough sector that it is possible for the authors to know the exact number of non-ALGEO members. This is not possible for England.

^{xi}Aitchison, K., & Rocks-Macqueen, D. 2013. Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13. Landward Research Ltd.

^{xii}Aitchison, K., 2019. State of the Archaeological Market 2017-18, Landward Research Ltd.

<https://landward.eu/blog/archaeological-market-survey-2017-18/>

^{xiii}Aitchison, K., & Rocks-Macqueen, D. 2013. Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13. Landward Research Ltd.

^{xiv}The Impact of Archaeology on Property Developments in the City of London, City of London, (2000?)

<https://www.cityoflondon.gov.uk/business/economic-research-and-information/research-publications/Documents/2007-2000/The-Impact-of-Archaeology-on-Property-Development.pdf>

^{xv}<http://www.constructionmanagermagazine.com/cpd-articles/cpd-digging-past/>

^{xvi}Balfour Beatty, Carillion, Laing O' Rourke, Interserve, Morgan Sindall, Kier, Galliford Try, ISG, Mitie, Skanska UK

^{xvii}<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-northern-ireland-25197874>

^{xviii}https://www.niauditoffice.gov.uk/sites/niao/files/media-files/december_2013_archaeological_claims_settlement.pdf

^{xix}<https://www.niauditoffice.gov.uk/publication/department-regional-development-archaeological-claims-settlement>

^{xx}<http://www.rosetheatre.org.uk/>

^{xxi}Aitchison, K. 2013, 'No going back – remembering when British archaeology changed forever' in J. Jameson & J. Eogan (eds), *Training and Practice for Modern Day Archaeologists*, 53-68. New York: Springer.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/302209410_No_Going_Back_Remembering_When_British_Archaeology_Changed_Forever

^{xxii}<https://www.mola.org.uk/blog/remains-shakespeare%E2%80%99s-curtain-theatre-discovered-shoreditch>

^{xxiii}<https://www.standard.co.uk/news/london/curtain-lifts-on-open-air-stage-at-shakespeare-theatre-site-in-shoreditch-8464712.html>

^{xxiv}<http://www.thestageshoreditch.com/archaeology>

^{xxv}<https://www.cityoflondon.gov.uk/business/economic-research-and-information/research-publications/Documents/2007-2000/The-Impact-of-Archaeology-on-Property-Development.pdf>

^{xxvi}Aitchison, K., 2019. State of the Archaeological Market 2017-18, Landward Research Ltd.

<https://landward.eu/blog/archaeological-market-survey-2017-18/>

^{xxvii}https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/590464/Fixing_our_broken_housing_market_-_print_ready_version.pdf

^{xxviii}<https://hansard.parliament.uk/Commons/2016-09-07?showNoDebateMessage=True>

^{xxix}<https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2016-10-10/debates/FB49DB14-51A5-4FBD-9820-018AF6FA4153/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill>

-
- ^{xxx}https://districtcouncils.info/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/161019-DCN-NR-Bill-v2-Committee-stage-Briefing_Final.pdf
- ^{xxxi}<https://www.nhbcfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/NF57-Improving-the-prospects-for-small-house-builders.pdf>
- ^{xxxii}https://www.nhbcfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/NF76_WEB.pdf
- ^{xxxiii}[https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2016-10-18/debates/716e4a04-7085-4b76-9b3d-9e8535ef9c05/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill\(FirstSitting\)](https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2016-10-18/debates/716e4a04-7085-4b76-9b3d-9e8535ef9c05/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill(FirstSitting))
- ^{xxxiv}<https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919202659/http://www.communities.gov.uk/publications/planningandbuilding/killianprettyfinal> (pp. 74)
- ^{xxxv}<https://www.fmb.org.uk/media/35090/fmb-house-builders-survey-2017.pdf>
- ^{xxxvi}[https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2016-10-25/debates/1d056baf-95ef-453e-8579-239aee4ed3b1/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill\(FifthSitting\)](https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2016-10-25/debates/1d056baf-95ef-453e-8579-239aee4ed3b1/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill(FifthSitting))
- ^{xxxvii}<https://hansard.parliament.uk/lords/2017-02-23/debates/200DB6D8-0B11-45A0-B3F0-C21A6BCA2FDC/NeighbourhoodPlanningBill>
- ^{xxxviii}https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/591039/house-building-cutting-red-tape-review.pdf
- ^{xxxix}<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld201617/ldselect/ldconaf/20/20.pdf>
- ^{xl}<https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/implementation-of-planning-changes-technical-consultation>
- ^{xli}<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/2010-to-2015-government-policy-house-building/2010-to-2015-government-policy-house-building>
- ^{xlii}https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7532/2033676.pdf
- ^{xliiii}<https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919182728/http://www.communities.gov.uk/documents/planningandbuilding/pdf/benchmarkingcostsapplication.pdf>
- ^{xliv}<https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919202659/http://www.communities.gov.uk/publications/planningandbuilding/killianprettyfinal>
- ^{xlv}https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7715/324923.pdf